

Phytochemical Analysis of Antibacterial activity and FT-IR analysis of leaf extract of *Justicia betonica* L.

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Abstract

Justicia betonica L. is a herb species belongs to genus *Justicia* and family Acanthaceae. The aim of the present study is to analyse qualitative, quantitative phytochemicals, FTIR analysis and antibacterial activities of Hexane, Ethyl acetate and Ethanol leaf extracts of *Justicia betonica* L. The antibacterial activity of different solvents at various concentrations of crude extract of *J. betonica* was tested by disc diffusion method against three bacterial pathogens: *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined for evaluating the potential plant extract. The quantitative phytochemical analysis of this species exhibited the presence of alkaloids, tannins, saponins, ascorbic acid, total phenolics, in considerable quantity and bacterial growth was suppressed by various plant concentrations. The functional groups of leaf extract were analysed by FT-IR method. In this analysis, ethanol leaf extract shows five functional groups. The major peak value was characterized at wavelength of 3365.8 to 1397.8 which indicates hydroxyl (O-H), sulfoxide (S=O) functional group.

Keywords: *Justicia betonica* , Phytochemical analysis, Antibacterial and FT-IR.

1. Introduction

Recently, the World Health Organization reports that at least 75 - 95% of the world populations of developing countries were chiefly rely on traditional medicines and major part of traditional therapies which involves the use of plant extract products or their active constituents. Plants are the basic source of knowledge of modern medicine. Almost all the parts of the plant, namely roots, stems, leaves, flowers, fruits, and seeds are known to have various medicinal properties. The trend of using natural products has increased and the active plant extracts are frequently screened for new drug discoveries [1]. WHO reports that around 80% of the world's population consumes medicinal plant products to cure various diseases [2]. It has been reported in many studies that antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, anti-viral, anti-bacterial, antifungal, insecticidal, anti-malarial, anti-aging and several other therapeutic activities depend on a considerable variety of secondary metabolites (glucosinolates, lycopenes, anthocyanidins, flavonoids, iso flavonoids , polyphenols, limonoids, carotenoids, phytoestrogens and omega-3 fatty acids, etc.) isolated from potential medicinal plants using advanced, sensitive and sophisticated equipment. Among these characteristics, about 20,000 species of plants have been researched for medicinal purposes [3]. In fact, naturally occurring antioxidants have attracted much interest in research into identifying secondary metabolites for the healthcare and food industries. Antioxidants can

maintain health by scavenging free radicals and reactive oxygen species [4]. Two-thirds of all plant species are said to have medicinal value and antioxidant potential [5]. The extraction and characterization of these bioactive compounds has led to the delivery of specific drugs with a high activity profile [6]. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) are widely used for functional group observation and identification of various bioactive compounds in plants [7,8]. Acanthaceae consists of about 4,300 species belonging to 346 genera and top 12 most diverse families. These plants are horticulturally important and cultivated as ornamental plant [9,10]. *Justicia* is an important genus of Acanthaceae, with approximately 700 species, with many unresolved species which are found in pantropical and tropical regions. *Justicia* species are reported to occur in tropical to warm temperate regions of America, India, Indonesia, Southeast Asia, Malaysia, Pakistan, and Africa.

In India, the inflorescence extract of this plant is given orally to treat vomiting and constipation and used externally to wash hairs [9]. Leaves are crushed and applied to relieve pain and swelling [10]. Leaf decoction is used to cure vomiting and headache. In Uganda, the leaves of *J. betonica* are used against HIV/AIDS. *J. betonica* is administered to lower cholesterol and is used to treat paralysis, ear aches, headaches, bruises, diarrhoea, vomiting, constipation, pain and inflammation, and malaria in India. The plant possesses analgesic, antimalarial, antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties [11,12].

Historically, all medicinal preparations were derived from plants, whether of raw plant materials or of refined crude extracts, mixtures, etc. Recent estimates suggest that several thousands of plants have been known with medicinal applications in various cultures [13]. Plants used in traditional medicine contain a vast array of substances that can be used to treat chronic and infectious diseases. Medicinal herbs practiced in traditional folk medicine in India were screened for the presence of antibacterial activity. The usage of plant parts as traditional medicine is the most common practice in India, particularly as folk-lore medicines. Due to continuous usage of antibiotics against clinical pathogens, development of drug resistance is a major problem now a day.

Antimicrobial agents are essentially important in reducing the global burden of infectious diseases [14]. However, emergence and dissemination of multidrug resistant (MDR) strain in pathogenic bacteria have become a significant public health threat as there are fewer, or even sometimes no, effective antimicrobial agents available for the infection caused by pathogenic bacteria [15,16]. Thus, in the light of the evidence of the rapid global spread of resistant clinical isolates, the need to find new antimicrobial agents is of paramount importance. However, the past record of rapid, widespread emergence of resistance to newly introduced antimicrobial agents indicates that even new families of antimicrobial agents will have a short life expectancy [18,19].

Due to increased and indiscriminate use of antibiotics for treatment of humans and animals there develops the antibiotic resistance and multidrug resistance microorganisms like *Salmonella* spp. which has increased a great deal in developing countries [19]. Only in the last two decades, studies focused on natural compounds with antioxidant activities have shown enormous growth, since a substantial amount of evidence has indicated that cell damage caused by oxidative stress has been considered an important factor in aging and in

the development of a wide variety of pathologies, such as autoimmune diseases, infectious and/or inflammatory diseases, and degenerative and neurodegenerative diseases [20].

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Collection of plant materials

Fresh leaves of *Justicia betonica* L. were collected from Karumbu Kadai, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India. The plant parts were washed carefully with running tap water, rinsed with distilled water and shade dried for a month. They were ground into fine powder by using mortar and pestle; stored in a room temperature.

2.2. Preparation of extracts

50 grams of dried leaf powder of *Justicia betonica* L. was successively extracted in Soxhlet apparatus using increasing polarity of solvents vis., hexane, ethyl acetate and ethanol of 250 ml each. The crude extracts were dried under reduced pressure using rotary vacuum evaporator to get the crude and were stored below 4°C until further use. The percentage yield of evaporated plant extracts was calculated as follows:

$$\frac{[\text{Extract} + \text{container}(g)] - [\text{Empty container}(g)]}{\text{Sample weight}(g)}$$

2.3. Preparation of test organisms

Escherichia coli, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (gram- negative) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram- positive) were bought as readymade culture from Bio line Laboratory, R. S. Puram, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India. The organisms were isolated in Muller Hinton agar medium and selectively cultured at 37°C for 24 hrs. The bacterial strains were identified by biochemical and standard antibiogram tests as per the directions from Bergy's manual for determinative bacteriology.

2.4. Qualitative test

phytochemical analysis (Harborne, 1973 and Sofowara, 1993). All the extracts were subjected to preliminary phytochemical analysis according to the following methods.

2.4.1. Detection of Alkaloids Dragendorff's test:

To 2ml of the plant extracts, 5ml of distilled water was added; 2ml Hydrochloric acid was added until an acid reaction occurs. To this 1ml Dragendorff's reagent was added. Formation of orange red precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

2.4.2. Detection of Flavonoids Shinoda's test (Magnesium Hydrochloride Reduction Test):

To 3-4ml of each extract, few fragments of magnesium metal were added in separate test tube followed by drop wise addition of concentrated HCl. Formation of magenta colour indicated the presence of flavonoids.

Lead acetate test: To 1ml of extract was mixed with few drops of 10% lead acetate. Formation of yellow precipitate showed that presence of flavonoid.

2.4.3. Detection of Glycosides Keller-Kiliani test:

To 2ml of extract, glacial acetic acid, one drop of FeCl_3 and concentrated H_2SO_4 was added on the sides of the test tube. A brown ring is formed at interface of two liquid layer indicates the presence of glycosides.

Legal's test: Few ml of each extract was added with 1 or 2 drops of 10% NaOH and make it alkaline. To the extract, add freshly prepared sodium nitroprusside solution. Appearance of blue col indicates the presence of glycosides.

2.4.4. Detection of Phenolic compounds Ferric Chloride test:

5 ml of the concentrated extracts were taken and 2ml of neutral ferric chloride solution was added. Appearance of violet colour indicates the presence of phenols.

2.4.5. Detection of Saponins Froth test:

1ml of distilled water was added to 10 drops of crude plant extracts dissolved and boiled with 10 ml distilled water in a test tube, shaken vigorously to froth and then allowed to persist for 10 -13 minutes. Saponins was measured by observing the height of froth: no froth (absence), froth less than 3mm (poor), froth of 6mm (moderate), and froth up to 1cm (abundant).

2.4.6. Detection of Steroids Libermann-Burchard's test:

2ml of each extract were taken and it is evaporated. Then the residues were dissolved in acetic anhydride solution and add chloroform. 2 drops of concentrated H_2SO_4 were added carefully along the sides of test tube. A brown ring is formed between supernatant layers showed the presence of steroids.

2.4.7. Detection of Tannins Braemer's test:

2ml of each extract was diluted with distilled water followed by the addition of 2-3 drops of 5% ferric chloride solution. Indication of green-black or blue-back colorization showed the presence of tannins.

2.4.9. Detection of Terpenoids Salkowski test:

2ml of chloroform and concentrated H_2SO_4 were added to 1ml of each extract. Appearance of reddish-brown colour indicates the presence of terpenoids.

2.4.10. Detection of carbohydrates Molisch's test:

About 3ml of extracts was added with 1ml of Molisch's reagent and 3 drops of concentrated sulphuric acid. Red or violet ring appears in the interface of two layers indicating the presence of carbohydrates.

2.5. Quantitative phytochemical analysis

Determination of total phenolics

The total phenolic content of plant extracts was determined using Folin-Ciocalteu reagent according to the procedure described by Siddhuraju and Becker (2003). In this method, 1 µg of the extract (dissolved in the respective solvent) was taken in a test tube and made up to the volume of 1.0 ml with distilled water. Then 0.5 ml of freshly prepared Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (1:1) with water and 2 ml of 20% of sodium carbonate solution were added sequentially in each tube. The mixtures were agitated and left in the dark at laboratory temperature for 40 min for the development of colour. The absorbance was recorded at 725 nm against the reagent blank using a Shimadzu-UV-160 spectrophotometer (Japan). A calibration curve of gallic acid was constructed and linearity was obtained. Using the standard curve, the total phenol content of the extract was calculated and expressed as gallic acid equivalent (GAE) mg/g extract.

2.6. Determination of antibacterial activity

Six concentrations of each extract (0.02 mg/mL, 0.4 mg/mL, 0.6 mg/mL, 0.8 mg/mL, 1.0 mg/mL, 1.2 mg/mL) were prepared and their antibacterial activity was assessed by disc diffusion method against test bacteria. Stock culture of test bacteria were grown in Nutrient agar broth medium at 37°C for 24 hrs. Final bacterial number were adjusted to 0.5 McFarland turbidometry. A lawn culture then prepared on Muller Hinton agar (MHA, Merck) using sterile cotton swab. Sterile 6mm filter discs were placed on the cultures and impregnated with 50 mcg of each concentration. The plates were left at room temperature for about 1 hours to allow the extract to diffuse from the disc into the medium and were then incubated at 37⁰C for 24 hrs. After incubation, the diameter of the zone of bacterial growth inhibition around each disc were measured and recorded in millimetre (mm). A standard antibiotic including Ampicillin (10 mcg) was used as controls for comparing the results. In order to determine the possible inhibitory effect of hexane on test bacteria, discs containing 80% hexane were also tested.

2.7. FTIR Analysis

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy is a specific type of infrared spectroscopy. Unlike a dispersive infrared spectrometer, where a dispersive element splits the incoming light into its spectral components and where each component is measured individually, one at a time (“scanned”), in FTIR, all frequencies of light are measured simultaneously. The infrared spectrum is then obtained via a mathematic conversion called Fourier transformation. Because FTIR spectroscopy measures all frequencies simultaneously, FTIR analysis can be performed much faster compared to a scanning technique.

In Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, all spectral components of the light source are detected together. In order to obtain an FTIR spectrum, the spectral composition of the incoming light is permanently modified. Therefore, the signal detected by the FTIR detector is time dependent. A mathematical operation called Fourier transformation allows us to convert the detector signal from a time domain into the frequency domain

(ultimately displayed in wavenumbers, cm^{-1}), which results in the well-known FTIR spectrum.

3. RESULT

3.1. Preliminary qualitative phytochemical analysis

The present study revealed that the various solvents extract of leaf of *Justicia betonica* contained alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, triterpenoids, carbohydrates, phenols, glycoside and steroids Table: 1. However, terpenoids, triterpenoids and steroids were detected only in ethyl acetate extract of leaf parts. Next to ethyl acetate extract, ethanol extract of leaf parts showed the presence of rich variety of secondary metabolites. Hexane extract showed the less variety of these secondary metabolites. Compared to other solvent extract ethyl acetate leaf extract had higher number of secondary metabolites with higher degree of precipitation. Mid polarity solvent of ethyl acetate has ability to extract secondary metabolites from *J. betonica*. It responds to ethyl acetate very much than other two solvents of hexane and ethanol. Triterpenoids and steroids were determined to present with lesser amount only in ethyl acetate solvent. Saponins and tannins are absent in all three solvents on leaf parts of *J. betonica* L.

3.2. Quantitative determination of the chemical constituency

Extraction yield

Table 2. shows the percentage of yield of crude successive extract (Hexane, Ethyl acetate and Ethanol) of leaf parts of *J. betonica*. Ethanolic extracts of leaf exhibited higher yield of 5.07% followed by hexane leaf extract showed the lowest yield of 3.2%. The ethyl acetate extracts showed the moderate amount of yield of 4.2%.

Table 1. Preliminary qualitative phytochemical analysis of various alcoholic and aqueous extracts of leaf of *J. betonica* L.

Plant constituents	Hexane	Ethyl acetate	Ethanol
Alkaloids	-	+	++
Flavonoids	+	-	+++
Terpenoids	-	++	-
Carbohydrates	-	+	+
Phenols	-	+	++
Glycosides	+	++	-
Saponins	-	-	-
Tannins	-	-	-
Steroids	-	+	++
Triterpenoids	-	+	-

+: Present, ++: Moderately present, +++: Highly present and -: Absent.

Total phenol content

Total phenol content of various extracts of leaf of *J. betonica* L. was varying widely between 0.064 to 2.626 mg GAE/100g extract (Table 2). Ethanolic extract of leaf were demonstrating higher total phenol content of 2.626 mg GAE/100g extracts than that of the other solvent extracts.

Table 2. Percentage yield, total phenol contents of various alcoholic and aqueous extracts of leaf part of *J. betonica* L.

Sample	Percentage yield (w/w)	Total phenol
Hexane	3.2	0.064
Ethyl acetate	4.2	0.122
Ethanol	5.7	2.626

3.3. Antibacterial activity

The results showed that antibacterial activities of leaf extract of *J. betonica* L is presented in table 3. This antibacterial activity was quantitatively determined by the presence or absence of inhibition zone around the discs containing extract. The ethanol extract shows the highest antibacterial activity at 1.2 g/mL with inhibition zone of 20.4 ± 1.13 mm against *Staphylococcus aureus* followed by inhibition zone of 20.2 ± 0.11 mm against *E. coli* and inhibition zone of 18.9 ± 0.19 mm against *K. pneumonia*. The ethyl acetate extract exhibited moderate antibacterial activity at 1.2 g/mL with the inhibition zone of 18.1 ± 0.14 mm against *E. coli* and inhibition zone of 16.1 ± 0.08 mm against *S. aureus* and inhibition zone of 13.2 ± 0.12 mm against *K. pneumonia*. The lowest antibacterial activity was recorded in hexane extract with the inhibition zone of 12.5 ± 0.12 mm at 1.2 g/mL against *K. pneumonia* followed by inhibition zone of 12.4 ± 0.11 mm against *E. coli* and inhibition zone of 12.3 ± 0.18 mm against *S. aureus*. The most resistance strains among 3 tested bacterial species is *S. aureus*. In fact, the used leaf extract had not significant antibacterial effect against *K. pneumoniae*. *J. betonica* L are nearly resistance to *K. pneumoniae* (at all six concentrations).

Table. 3. Antibacterial activity of different crude extracts of *Justicia betonica* leaf against pathogenic microorganisms using agar well diffusion method. Values are shown mean \pm SD of three replicates.

Sl. No.	Microorganisms/ Solvents Extracts	Mean zone of inhibition* (mm)						
		Concentration of leaf extract (mg/mL)						
		0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0	1.2	Control
1	<i>Escherichia coli</i>							
	Hexane	7.1 \pm 0.04	8.4 \pm 0.28	11.2 \pm 0.19	11.6 \pm 0.15	12.1 \pm 0.25	12.4 \pm 0.11	27.1 \pm 0.25
	Ethyl acetate	10.7 \pm 0.38	12.4 \pm 0.16	15.5 \pm 0.22	16.5 \pm 0.15	17.5 \pm 0.17	18.1 \pm 0.14	27.5 \pm 0.15
	Ethanol	12.2 \pm 0.16	14.1 \pm 0.39	17.4 \pm 0.13	18.5 \pm 0.07	19.5 \pm 0.09	20.2 \pm 0.11	28.7 \pm 0.15
2	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>							
	Hexane	8.5 \pm 0.25	9.3 \pm 0.38	11.0 \pm 0.27	11.4 \pm 0.25	11.9 \pm 0.12	12.3 \pm 0.18	19.2 \pm 0.58
	Ethyl acetate	10.1 \pm 0.18	11.6 \pm 0.17	13.7 \pm 0.18	14.7 \pm 0.18	15.6 \pm 0.17	16.1 \pm 0.08	18.7 \pm 0.12
	Ethanol	11.4 \pm 0.20	13.5 \pm 0.15	16.8 \pm 0.21	18.1 \pm 0.14	19.4 \pm 0.21	20.4 \pm 1.13	19.9 \pm 0.35
3	<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>							
	Hexane	9.7 \pm 0.30	10.3 \pm 0.22	11.2 \pm 0.11	11.5 \pm 0.25	12.2 \pm 0.28	12.5 \pm 0.12	19.1 \pm 0.25
	Ethyl acetate	9.8 \pm 0.13	10.6 \pm 0.16	11.8 \pm 0.35	12.2 \pm 0.22	12.8 \pm 0.11	13.2 \pm 0.12	18.2 \pm 0.15
	Ethanol	11.3 \pm 0.22	13.3 \pm 0.15	15.7 \pm 0.13	17.3 \pm 0.15	18.3 \pm 0.19	18.9 \pm 0.19	19.2 \pm 0.28

3.4. FTIR analysis

The ethanol leaf extract of *Justicia betonica* was evaluated for FT-IR analysis to determine the functional groups present in it. In IR spectrum, peaks with their absorption intensities, vibration type, band assignment and type of compounds are given in table 4. Five functional groups (O-H, S=O, C=C, C-H, C=C) in strong peaks were detected at 3365.8, 1043.7, 1621.21, 898.3 and 980.3 cm^{-1} respectively. These peaks are confirmed the presence of hydroxyl, sulphate, conjugated alkene, alkenes, sulfoxide, etc.

Fig 1. FT- IR spectrum of ethanol leaves extract of *Justicia betonica*

Table 4. Interpretation of the FT- IR spectrum of ethanol leaves extract of *Justicia betonica*

S.No.	Frequency(Cm ⁻¹)	Absorption intensity	Vibration type	Band Assignment	Type of Compounds
1	3365.8	Strong broad	Stretching Alcohol	O-H	Hydroxyl
2	2922.2	medium sharp	Stretching	C-H	Alkane
3	2857.4	medium sharp	Stretching	C-H	Alkane
4	2113.4	weak broad	Stretching	C≡C	Alkane
5	1338.1	medium sharp	Symmetric Stretching	N-O	nitro compound
6	1621.21	Strong sharp	Stretching	C=C	Conjugated alkene
7	1043.7	Narrow sharp	stretching	S=O	Sulfoxide
8	898.3	strong sharp	Bending	C-H	Alkane
9	980.3	strong sharp	Bending	C=C	Alkane

4. Discussion

Phytochemicals possess diverse protective and therapeutic effects [24]. It has been well documented that about 80% of the world's population directly or indirectly primarily depend on herbal medicines for their primary healthcare as they are readily available and are also less toxic [25,26]. Medicinal plants are an affluent source of phytochemical compounds that can play a vital role to treat several chronic diseases [27]. An extensive number of potent biomolecules come from a diverse number of medicinal plants in recent times [28]. Scientists believed that these potent chemical constituents obtained from nature are used for treating many disorders with fewer side effects [29]. *J. betonica* plays a significant role in folk as well as in veterinary medicines but, it is a less explored plant species as compared to its traditional usefulness as well as its antibacterial activity. Traditionally used medicinal plants produce variety of components with known therapeutic properties. The substances that can either inhibit the growth of pathogen or kill them and have no or least toxicity to host cells are considered candidates for developing new antibacterial drugs. Medicinal herbs are the local heritage with global importance. Medicinal herbs have curative properties due to the presence of various complex chemical substance of different composition, which are found as secondary plant metabolites in one or more parts of these plants. Secondary metabolites play a major role in the medicinal properties of plants.

Preliminary qualitative phytochemical analysis made for the leaf part of *J. betonica* L. revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, carbohydrates, phenol, glycoside, steroids, triterpenoids, with absence of saponins and tannins. The secondary metabolites are reported to have many biological and therapeutic properties, so this species is expected to have medicinal uses. The extraction yield calculated for hexane, ethyl acetate and ethanol extract of leaf part of *J. betonica* L. showed that ethanol extract registered higher percentage of yield. It may be due to high polarity of ethanol solvent which can draw high variety of plant constituents that other solvents did.

Generally, majority of the secondary metabolites studied in the leaf parts of *J. betonica* L. have present with higher amount in ethyl acetate extract than of the other alcoholic and aqueous solvents. It is explained that the polarity level and species nature are playing major role in extracting the secondary metabolites.

The results of this study showed that *J. betonica* L. extract had not any antibacterial activity against *K. pneumoniae*. The result demonstrated that *S. aureus* exhibited resistance to all of the tested antibiotics. However, the solvent and the extraction system may both modify the final results and suitable solvent is important to get maximum antibacterial activity. For example, Babu *et al*, 2008 showed that the antibacterial activity is more significant in solvent extracts as compared to aqueous extract in all the plants indicating that the active principle responsible for antibacterial activity is more soluble in organic solvents. Sasikumar *et al.* in 2007 reported that the extract of *J. betonica* failed to inhibit the growth of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Salmonella Typhi*, and *V. cholera* [20]. The leaf extract of this plant is reported to be active against rice moth, *Coraryra* [21]. Ssenyondo *et al.* in 2020 reported that the leaf extract of *Justicia betonia* shows antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus* [22]. According to Correa and Alcantara 2012, lignans are the major components of the active extracts of the species of *Justicia*, exhibiting important pharmacological properties, such as antiviral, antitumoral, anti-inflammatory, and antiplatelet aggregation activities, which warrant further

exploration [23]. Here, we found the whole plant extract inhibit the growth of *S. mutans*, *S. pyogenes*, *V. cholerae*, and *S. flexneri*. The result of the study contributes to the scientific validation for the use of these medicinal plants in traditional medicine and serve as a guide for selection of plants with antibacterial activity for further phytochemical work on the isolation and identification of the active compounds.

5. Conclusion

In this study, we concluded that *J. betonica* L. Ethanol leaf extract of FT-IR shows the alkene and sulfate functional groups of this plant. Plant contains almost all-important types of phytochemical constituents and possesses antibacterial potential at various concentrations. Ethyl acetate and ethanol fraction extracts had very high phytochemical constitutions, subsequently, hexane have very small number of secondary metabolites. Ethanol mixed assay which inhibits the growth of *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. So, this plant is used for bacterial infections at various dosage.

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